

Minimal work dissipated in a complete flip-flop cycle in the limit of zero switching time

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Abstract

An expression for the minimum dissipated energy per cycle of a physical system that can be switched by external action between two stable configurations 1 and 2 (flip-flop) is derived for the limit of zero switching time. The system is assumed to be in contact with a thermostat at temperature T . The result is obtained on the basis of the general formalism of quantum mechanics and of the principles of thermodynamics with no assumptions about the physical nature of the device except that the switching process is controlled by a set of real parameters, *e.g.* the components of external electric or magnetic fields. The resulting expression is evaluated for a model Hamiltonian representing the essential features of the cycle. Due to thermal fluctuations, the system may be in configuration 2 with probability δ_1 , although the values of the external parameters are set according to configuration 1, and similarly with probability δ_2 in the opposite instance. These probabilities must be small for a reliable operation of the flip-flop. For the choice $\delta_1 = \delta_2 = 0.5 \times 10^{-9}$, the model Hamiltonian yields a minimum dissipated energy of $1.8 \times 10^{-9} \text{ J} \approx 1.1 \text{ eV}$ per cycle and bit required for the fast operation of a reliable flip-flop at 300 K.

Physical systems that can be switched by external action between two stable configurations (flip-flops) are crucial elements of digital information storage and information processing hardware. To switch a flip-flop from one to the other configuration and back again causes energy dissipation. The minimal dissipated energy per cycle of operation goes to zero if the process is driven arbitrarily slowly; it augments with increasing operation speed. To possess information about the minimal amount of dissipated energy for a flip-flop operated very fast is interesting in several respects. The aim of the present work is to provide such information. It owes much to ideas presented by C. Jarzynski in ref. [1].

The minimal work W_{\min}^{diss} dissipated in case of infinitely fast switching

A flip-flop is considered here as a quantum mechanical system with Hamilton operator

$$H = H(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{r}(t)) \quad (1)$$

in contact with a thermostat with inverse temperature $\beta = 1/(k_B T)$. The operators \mathbf{A} denote the inner variables of the system, the time dependent vector $\mathbf{r}(t)$ a set of real parameters driven by external forces from \mathbf{r}_1 at time 0 to \mathbf{r}_2 at time t_s and back from \mathbf{r}_2 to \mathbf{r}_1 later on. The system is initially in thermal equilibrium with the thermostat and with respect to the Hamiltonian

$$H_1 \equiv H(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{r}_1) \quad (2)$$

i.e. it is in the Gibbs state

$$\rho_1^{\text{sys}} = \frac{e^{-\beta H_1}}{\text{Tr}(e^{-\beta H_1})} \quad (3)$$

The inner energy U^{sys} of the system equals then

$$U_1^{\text{sys}} = \langle H_1 \rangle_1 = \frac{\text{Tr}(H_1 e^{-\beta H_1})}{\text{Tr}(e^{-\beta H_1})} \quad (4)$$

The following cycle of operation, subdivided into four partial processes, will now be considered:

- I** The system is isolated from the thermostat and the parameters \mathbf{r} are driven very fast by external forces from the value \mathbf{r}_1 to the value \mathbf{r}_2 . The limit $t_s \rightarrow 0$ is evaluated.
- II** The system is brought into contact to the thermostat. Thermal relaxation is attended, while \mathbf{r} is held fixed at the value \mathbf{r}_2 implying that there is no energy exchange with the external forces.
- III** The system is isolated from the thermostat and \mathbf{r} is driven very fast from \mathbf{r}_2 to \mathbf{r}_1 .
- IV** The system is brought into contact to the thermostat and thermal relaxation is attended, while \mathbf{r} is held fixed at the value \mathbf{r}_1 .

The system is in its initial configuration again if process **IV** is accomplished and the cycle is closed.

Process **I** is evaluated in the *Heisenberg picture* where the state of the system is considered constant in time. The operators are time dependent their dynamics being determined by the Heisenberg equation

$$\frac{d}{dt} \mathbf{A}(t) = \frac{i}{\hbar} [H(\mathbf{A}(t), \mathbf{r}(t)), \mathbf{A}(t)] \quad (5)$$

In order to calculate the limit $t_s \rightarrow 0$ we substitute $\tau = t/t_s$, $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}(\tau) = \mathbf{r}(t_s\tau)$, $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\tau) = \mathbf{A}(t_s\tau)$ and take the integral of the resulting equation within the limits $\tau = 0$ and $\tau = 1$, which yields, with $\mathbf{A}(0) = \mathbf{A}(1) = \mathbf{A}$,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}}(1) = \mathbf{A} + t_s \frac{i}{\hbar} \int_0^1 d\tau [H(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\tau), \tilde{\mathbf{r}}(\tau)), \tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\tau)] \quad (6)$$

It immediately follows that

$$\lim_{t_s \downarrow 0} \tilde{\mathbf{A}}(1) = \mathbf{A} \quad (7)$$

The inner variables are frozen to their initial values \mathbf{A} in an infinitely fast, adiabatic switching process [1] and the Hamiltonian at the end of process **I** is

$$H_2 \equiv H(\mathbf{A}(t_s), \mathbf{r}_2) = H(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}(1), \mathbf{r}_2) = H(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{r}_2) \quad (8)$$

The Hamiltonians H_1 and H_2 characterize the two stable configurations of the flip-flop. The change of the inner energy of the system due to process **I** is given by

$$\langle H_2 \rangle_1 - \langle H_1 \rangle_1 \quad (9)$$

which is, for the adiabatic process, equal to the work provided by the external forces.

Process **II** is evaluated in the *Schrödinger picture*, where the operators are constant and the time evolution is carried by the states. Recourse is taken to thermodynamics, which states that a system with constant Hamiltonian H_2 and in contact with a thermostat with inverse temperature β relaxes to the Gibbs state ρ_2^{sys} . The change of the inner energy of the system due to process **II** is given by

$$\langle H_2 \rangle_2 - \langle H_2 \rangle_1 \quad (10)$$

this difference being dissipated by the thermostat as heat.

Processes **III** and **IV** are evaluated accordingly. The results are summarized in the table below:

pro- cess	ΔW^{ext}	ΔU^{th}	ΔU^{sys}
I	$-\langle H_2 \rangle_1 + \langle H_1 \rangle_1$	0	$\langle H_2 \rangle_1 - \langle H_1 \rangle_1$
II	0	$-\langle H_2 \rangle_2 + \langle H_2 \rangle_1$	$\langle H_2 \rangle_2 - \langle H_2 \rangle_1$
III	$-\langle H_1 \rangle_2 + \langle H_2 \rangle_2$	0	$\langle H_1 \rangle_2 - \langle H_2 \rangle_2$
IV	0	$-\langle H_1 \rangle_1 + \langle H_1 \rangle_2$	$\langle H_1 \rangle_1 - \langle H_1 \rangle_2$
total cycle	$-\langle H_2 \rangle_1 + \langle H_1 \rangle_1$ $-\langle H_1 \rangle_2 + \langle H_2 \rangle_2$	$-\langle H_2 \rangle_2 + \langle H_2 \rangle_1$ $-\langle H_1 \rangle_1 + \langle H_1 \rangle_2$	0

Taking all in all, the work

$$W_{\text{min}}^{\text{diss}} = \langle H_2 \rangle_1 - \langle H_2 \rangle_2 + \langle H_1 \rangle_2 - \langle H_1 \rangle_1 \quad (11)$$

is transferred from the external source to the thermostat during a cycle and is dissipated there. Each intermediate process of the cycle is indispensable. The considerations above are uniquely based on the quantum mechanical formalism and the principles of thermodynamics with no specific assumptions taken about the physical nature of the device except that it can be described by a Hamiltonian of the form (1). The expression (11) is, therefore, a device independent, lower limit of the dissipated energy per cycle. Additional dissipative processes occur in real devices *e.g.* in connection with the switching mechanisms in processes **I** and **III**, or in connection with the transfer of the external work to the device, or if relaxation is forced in processes **II** and **IV** in order to shorten relaxation time.

$W_{\text{min}}^{\text{diss}}$ only depends on the Hamiltonians H_1 and H_2 , characterizing the two stable configurations of the flip-flop, and on the two corresponding Gibbs states ρ_1^{sys} and ρ_2^{sys} . It is, by the way, not necessary, in the limit considered, to assume that the system has been separated from the thermostat in processes **I** and **III**. To add an interaction term $H^{\text{int}}(\mathbf{A}^{\text{th}}, \mathbf{A}, \mathbf{r})$, which is needed to enable thermal relaxation, to the Hamiltonian $H(\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{r})$ in eq. (6) does not impair the result (7) and the heat exchange between system and thermostat can be neglected: the infinitely fast process is adiabatic.

The value of $W_{\text{min}}^{\text{diss}}$ for a model Hamiltonian

The following simple model Hamiltonian comprises the essential features of the problem. A 2-dimensional Hilbert space is assumed. Let $\{\psi_1^1, \psi_2^1\}$ and $\{\psi_1^2, \psi_2^2\}$ denote the eigenbases of H_1 and H_2 and Q_1 and Q_2 the projectors onto ψ_1^1 and ψ_2^2 . We set

$$\begin{aligned} H_1 &= -E_1 Q_1 \\ H_2 &= -E_2 Q_2 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

with $E_j > 0$, the energy levels belonging to the eigenstates ψ_2^1 and ψ_1^2 being set equal to 0, and choose the operator

$$S = Q_1 - Q_2 \quad (13)$$

as pointer observable.

A straightforward calculation yields

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle Q_1 \rangle_1 &= \frac{e^{\beta E_1}}{e^{\beta E_1} + 1} \\
\langle Q_2 \rangle_1 &= \frac{qe^{\beta E_1} + 1 - q}{e^{\beta E_1} + 1} \equiv \delta_1 \\
\langle Q_1 \rangle_2 &= \frac{1 - q + qe^{\beta E_2}}{e^{\beta E_2} + 1} \equiv \delta_2 \\
\langle Q_2 \rangle_2 &= \frac{e^{\beta E_2}}{e^{\beta E_2} + 1}
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

with

$$q = (\psi_1^1, Q_2 \psi_1^1) = (\psi_2^2, Q_1 \psi_2^2) = |(\psi_2^2, \psi_1^1)|^2, \quad 0 \leq q \leq 1 \tag{15}$$

The relationships $\text{Tr } Q_1 = \text{Tr } Q_2 = 1$ have been used. One gets from Eqns. (14)

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle S \rangle_1 &= \frac{1 - q}{1 - 2q} (1 - 2\delta_1) \\
\langle S \rangle_2 &= \frac{1 - q}{1 - 2q} (-1 + 2\delta_2)
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

δ_1 denotes the probability that a measurement of the observable Q_2 on the system prepared into the Gibbs state ρ_1^{sys} indicates the configuration 2 of the flip-flop instead of the expected configuration 1 because of thermal fluctuations and of a nonorthogonality of ψ_1^1 and ψ_2^2 . The probabilities δ_1 and δ_2 must be small in order to assure a reliable operation of the flip-flop. It is $\delta = q + (1 - 2q)/(e^{\beta E} + 1)$ and δ monotonically tends from 1/2 for $E = 0$ to q for $E \rightarrow +\infty$. δ can attain small values only if q is small and it is then $\delta > q$ for finite values of $E > 0$.

With eqs. (11), (12), and (14), one obtains

$$W_{\min}^{\text{diss}} = (1 - q)(E_1 + E_2) \frac{(e^{\beta(E_1 + E_2)} - 1)}{(e^{\beta E_1} + 1)(e^{\beta E_2} + 1)} \tag{17}$$

$$+ q(E_1 - E_2) \frac{(e^{\beta E_1} - e^{\beta E_2})}{(e^{\beta E_1} + 1)(e^{\beta E_2} + 1)} \tag{18}$$

Both summands are bigger or equal than zero. In terms of δ_1 , δ_2 , and q instead of E_1 , E_2 , and q , it is

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta W_{\min}^{\text{diss}} &= \left(\ln \frac{1 - \delta_1 - q}{\delta_1 - q} + \ln \frac{1 - \delta_2 - q}{\delta_2 - q} \right) (1 - \delta_1 - \delta_2) \\
&+ \frac{q}{1 - 2q} \left((1 - 2\delta_1) \ln \frac{1 - \delta_1 - q}{\delta_1 - q} + (1 - 2\delta_2) \ln \frac{1 - \delta_2 - q}{\delta_2 - q} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

$\beta W_{\min}^{\text{diss}}$ decreases with decreasing values of q for fixed values of δ_1 and δ_2 , if $0 \leq q < \delta_1$, $\delta_2 < 1/2$. Therefore, a minimum value of W_{\min}^{diss} is attained, for fixed values of δ_1 and δ_2 , if $q = 0$ i.e. if ψ_1^1 and ψ_2^2 are orthogonal, $\{\psi_1^1, \psi_2^2\}$ then being an eigenbasis of H_1 , H_2 , and S . The switching processes consist in lowering and rising the energy levels of the two energy eigenstates without altering the states. It is in this case

$$\begin{aligned}
W_{\min}^{\text{diss}} &= -k_B T (\ln \delta_1 + \ln \delta_2 + O(\delta_1 + \delta_2)) (1 - (\delta_1 + \delta_2)) \\
&= (E_1 + E_2) (1 + O(e^{-\beta E_1} + e^{-\beta E_2}))
\end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Choosing, somewhat arbitrarily, $2\delta_1 = 2\delta_2 = 10^{-9}$ yields $\beta W_{\min}^{\text{diss}} \approx 42.83$; or a minimum dissipated energy of about $1.8 \times 10^{-19} \text{ J} \approx 1.1 \text{ eV}$ per cycle and bit is required for the reliable operation of a flip-flop at 300 K.

References

- [1] C. Jarzynski, “Nonequilibrium Equality for Free Energy Differences”, Phys. Rev. Lett. **78**, 2690 – 2693 (1997)